

Search string adaptation across scientific databases

Database	Search string
SCOPUS	ALL(“social debt” OR “non-technical debt”) AND ALL(“agile” OR “large-scale” OR “large scale” OR “remote work” OR “distributed” OR “global” OR “scaled” OR “virtual work”) AND ALL(“software development”)
ACM Digital Library	(“social debt” OR “non-technical debt” AND (“agile” OR “large-scale” OR “large scale” OR “remote” OR “distributed” OR “global” OR “scaled” OR “virtual work”) AND “software development”)
Web of Science	TS=((“social debt” OR “non-technical debt”) AND (“agile” OR “large-scale” OR “large scale” OR “remote work” OR “distributed” OR “global” OR “scaled” OR “virtual work”) AND (“software development”))
Science Direct	(“social debt” OR “non-technical debt”) AND “software development” AND (“agile” OR “large-scale” OR “remote work” OR “distributed”)
SpringerLink	("social debt" OR "non-technical debt")AND ("agile" OR "large-scale" OR "remote work" OR "distributed" OR "global" OR "scaled" OR "virtual work") AND ("software development")
IEEE Xplore	((“social debt” OR “non-technical debt”) AND (“agile” OR “large-scale” OR “large scale” OR “remote” OR “distributed” OR “global” OR “scaled” OR “virtual work”) AND “software development”)